

Unification of treatments and interventions for tinnitus patients

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Deliverable D4.2:

Analysis of Medical Adherence on Existing m-health Data

Deliverable No. D14 – WP4

Authors	Laura Basso (UHREG), Winfried Schlee (UHREG), Myra Spiliopoulou (MAG)
Responsible of Deliverable	Myra Spiliopoulou (MAG)
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Table of contents

1	Introduction	3
2	User-centric and whole-stream learning	4
3	Patient neighborhood	5
4	Medical adherence in mHealth data	6
4.1	Identifying phases with varying dropout rates and predicting periods of inactivity...	6
4.2	Using missingness information to process time series with large gaps	7
4.3	Approach to estimate absenteeism	7
5	Medical adherence in clinical data	9
6	Conclusion	10
7	References.....	10

1 Introduction

The aim of work package 4 within UNITI is the harmonization of technical solutions and the objective of the task presented here is the analysis of medical adherence on existing m-health data. User-interaction metadata from the mHealth applications will be used to predict the adherence-levels of the users in the system. The analysis will incorporate expert knowledge on tinnitus from the clinical partners to analyze how the various factors can affect adherence on the mHealth applications. This deliverable is focused on predictors of medical adherence and phenotypes associated to medical adherence. Since the work of this work package had to be carried out while the UNITI RCT project was not concluded yet, we applied the methods and algorithms on already existing datasets of similar app projects (e.g. TrackYourTinnitus or TinnitusTips).

As part of work package 3 (analysis of existing data), ensemble models for treatment improvement prediction were developed and presented in deliverable D3.3. Included in this work were analyses applied to mHealth data to identify predictors of tinnitus-related symptoms. Further analysis and algorithm development on this mHealth data were undertaken by the UNITI team for WP4 and are reported here. The developed algorithms include user-centric and whole-stream learning (Shahania et al., 2021) and patient neighborhoods (Unnikrishnan et al. 2021) and are described in chapter 2 and 3.

mHealth applications allow for real-time data recording, which can provide valuable insights into treatment processes. However, as such applications rely on voluntary usage, the generated datasets are highly susceptible to fluctuating engagement and high user dropout rates. This poses challenges when applying machine learning techniques to the data. Moreover, in order to design measures that promote patient engagement with mHealth apps, it is necessary to predict and understand decline in engagement. Methods developed to deal with these challenges are presented in chapter 4.

In chapter 4.2, a method to identify phases with varying dropout rates in mHealth datasets and to predict expected periods of inactivity is presented (Schleicher et al. 2022a). When users pause or stop interacting with the app, this leads to ‘gaps’ in the time series data of varying duration. In chapter 4.3, a method is presented that uses the missingness information to process time series with large gaps (Schleicher et al. 2022b). This approach can handle time series of different sizes and with missing values to predict the adherence of an mHealth app user. In chapter 4.4, an approach is presented that allows to estimate the possible duration of a user’s absence. This approach provides a valuable tool for experts to better assess the adherence of users to self-monitoring apps and to take appropriate measures (Schleicher et al. 2022c).

Moreover, findings on medical adherence in clinical data is presented in chapter 5. Adherence to the completion of questionnaires was found to be an important factor in predicting post-treatment data in two tinnitus treatment centers (Puga et al. 2022).

2 User-centric and whole-stream learning

The first approach focused on algorithm development on mHealth data which links the clinic-centered predictors of WP3 with the mHealth outcomes of WP4 is focused on user-centric and whole-stream learning. It was presented at the IEEE 34th International Symposium on Computer-Based Medical Systems (CBMS) and was accepted for publication as a peer-reviewed manuscript (Shahania et al. 2021, entitled: “User-centric vs whole-stream learning for EMA prediction”, <https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/document/9474661>). The way users interact with an mHealth app can be thought of as a stochastic process that can be learned by an algorithm over the whole data stream. However, it's unclear if this process is the same for all users. This study investigates whether learning a separate model for each user leads to better predictions compared to learning one model for the whole data stream. Data from a pilot study on an mHealth app (called “TinnitusTips”) were used, where one group received non-personalized tips throughout the study and the other group received tips only in the second half. We propose a method that combines user-centric and global stream learning for predicting Ecological Momentary Assessments (EMA) using a Contextual Multi-Armed Bandit (CMAB) that takes into account the context of each user group and the quality of each learner's predictions. Figure 2.1 shows the architecture of the approach. This work showed that user-centric learning is better for users who contribute many EMA, while a learner over the entire data stream is better for users with few EMA. This work demonstrates the importance of a well-selected level architecture to model EMA data on tinnitus.

Figure 2.1 Overview of the three level architecture and the components at each level.

3 Patient neighborhood

The second approach focused on algorithm development on mHealth data which links the clinic-centered predictors of WP3 with the mHealth outcomes of WP4 is focused on patient neighborhood. This work was presented at the IEEE 34th International Symposium on Computer-Based Medical Systems (CBMS) and was accepted for publication as a peer-reviewed manuscript (Unnikrishnan et al. 2021, entitled “Love thy Neighbours: A Framework for Error-Driven Discovery of Useful Neighbourhoods for One-Step Forecasts on EMA data”, <https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/document/9474685>). The collection of disease-specific time series data through EMA can help to create personalized predictors for disease forecasting, which can be crucial for preemptive interventions. However, there is a common issue in EMA data where some users provide most of the data while most users contribute very little. To address this, the proposed framework aims to discover a useful neighborhood of “long” users for “short” ones by optimizing for the error of user-level predictors with little data available for learning. This is done by iteratively adding the next-most-similar long user from a similarity-ordered list if the error of the learned model does not increase. The training process is shown in Figure 3.1. The method was compared against a baseline that exploits all available data for long users and an exhaustive search model that retains only those users that yield the lowest error predictor. The method was tested on two different mHealth datasets and showed a significant improvement in accuracy while using less data than the standard method.

Figure 3.1 Flowchart of the workflow of the training process.

4 Medical adherence in mHealth data

Three approaches have been developed as part of WP4 to analyze and predict medical adherence in mHealth data.

4.1 Identifying phases with varying dropout rates and predicting periods of inactivity

mHealth app data are often affected by fluctuating engagement and high user dropout rates, which complicate the handling of this data. We proposed a method to identify phases with varying dropout rates and predict the expected period of inactivity in mHealth app data. This work was presented at the 20th International Conference on Artificial Intelligence in Medicine, where it also won the best paper award, and was accepted for publication as a peer-reviewed manuscript (Schleicher et al. 2022a, entitled: “When can I expect the mHealth user to return? Prediction meets time series with gaps”, 10.3389/fnins.2022.836834). The method to investigate a mHealth dataset for varying phases of attrition was applied and predicted if a user might reach the next phase from the current status. Change point detection was used to identify phases and time series classification to predict the user's phase. The approach is displayed in Figure 4.1. The method was evaluated on an mHealth app for tinnitus (called “TrackYourTinnitus”) and shows that it is appropriate for studying adherence in datasets with uneven, unaligned time series of different lengths and with missing values.

Fig. 4.1. Big Picture. (a) Attrition curve, (b) Phases of attrition, (c) Predicting the phases, (d) A time series represented as sequences (symbolized example), (e) Sequences with labeled gaps, (f) Predicting the return

4.2 Using missingness information to process time series with large gaps

Detecting and reacting to deterioration in user engagement is important for the improvement of adherence to self-monitoring apps. We propose a novel approach to predicting user behavior in mHealth apps by modeling patterns of absence instead of imputing missing values. This work was presented at the IEEE 35th International Symposium on Computer-Based Medical Systems (CBMS) and was accepted for publication as a peer-reviewed manuscript (Schleicher et al. 2022b, entitled: “Prediction of declining engagement to self-monitoring apps on the example of tinnitus mHealth data”, 10.1109/CBMS55023.2022.00047). The proposed approach can handle time series of different sizes and with missing values. Figure 5.1. shows how the presence and absence of daily entries is used to model adherence. The evaluation of the approach was carried out on two real-world mHealth datasets, and it was found that all algorithms outperformed the baseline and were able to handle a large quantity of missing values. Based on this work, it is recommended that mHealth app designers create mechanisms that highlight the duration of gaps and implement measures that motivate interaction with the app.

Fig. 5.1: Using the presence and absence of daily entries to model adherence. The segments YES and NO of the time series refer to the adherence in the corresponding segments.

4.3 Approach to estimate absenteeism

A method to estimate absenteeism in mHealth apps, i.e., the duration of gaps in time series data was developed. This work was presented at the IEEE 9th International Conference on Data Science and Advanced Analytics (DSAA) and was accepted for publication as a peer-reviewed manuscript (Schleicher et al. 2022c, entitled: “Expect the gap: A recommender

approach to estimate the absenteeism of self-monitoring mHealth app users”, 10.1109/DSAA54385.2022.10032390). The method combines binning, clustering, and collaborative filtering techniques to estimate how long a user of an mHealth app is absent. To address this, the users' time series data is decomposed into sequences with no gaps and associated with the duration of the subsequent gap. These gap durations are then sorted into categories and used for unsupervised time series clustering. This allows for the estimation of gap duration even if the same sequence has not been observed for the user. The different steps of the method are displayed in Figure 6.1. The results show that the quality of the clustering depends on the number of categories, technique used, and maximum length of gaps. K-Medoids and Agglomerative Clustering produced applicable results, and SVD++ was used for matrix factorization. The approach provides a valuable tool for assessing user adherence to self-monitoring apps. The approach allows medical experts to assess user adherence and decide if their absence is too long for the underlying protocols, targeting their resources accordingly.

Fig. 6.1: Big Picture. (a) Sequence generation, (b) Unsupervised binning to learn gap ratings, (c) Clustering of the time series sequences, (d) Matrix factorization of the clustered sequences

5 Medical adherence in clinical data

Regarding medical adherence in clinical data, a study was performed that compared tinnitus patients' profiles from two clinical centers involved in the UNITI project, focusing on questionnaire scores, sociodemographics, and adherence. This work was published as a peer-reviewed manuscript in *Frontiers of Neuroscience* (Puga et al. 2022, entitled: "Juxtaposing Medical Centers Using Different Questionnaires Through Score Predictors", 10.3389/fnins.2022.818686). Significant differences between the patient population profiles were found. Moreover, it was found that information on adherence in the common questionnaire(s) is a useful addition in the cross-center prediction scenario and that adherence

to questionnaire completion is an important factor in predicting post-treatment data. This highlights the importance of considering adherence for the analysis of clinical data.

6 Conclusion

In this report, we presented two methods developed in WP3 that are relevant to medical adherence (chapter 2: user-centric learning, chapter 3: patient neighborhood), three approaches developed in WP4 to analyze and predict medical adherence in mHealth data (chapter 4), and one work addressing adherence in clinical data (chapter 5). The three approaches that focus on medical adherence in mHealth data (chapter 4) address the challenges of fluctuating engagement and high user dropout rates associated with this type of data. The first approach (4.1.) uses change point detection and time series classification to identify phases with varying dropout rates and predict the expected period of inactivity in mHealth app data. This approach was evaluated and found to be suitable for studying adherence in mHealth datasets. The second approach (4.2.) is to model patterns of absence to predict user behavior in mHealth apps. The evaluation of the approach was carried out on two mHealth datasets and it was shown that the approach can handle time series of different sizes and with missing values. The third approach (4.3.) estimates the duration of gaps in time series data generated by mHealth apps. The approach provides a valuable tool for evaluating the adherence of users to self-monitoring apps and allows experts to better assess the phases of user absence and to take appropriate actions. In summary, the presented approaches have proven useful for analyzing mHealth app data and for assessing and predicting user adherence. The application of these methods can help to better understand and monitor patient adherence, providing new opportunities to personalize treatment and improving overall patient outcomes.

7 References

Puga, C., Schleicher, M., Niemann, U., Unnikrishnan, V., Boecking, B., Brueggemann, P., Simoes, J., Langguth, B., Schlee, W., Mazurek, B., & Spiliopoulou, M. (2022). Juxtaposing Medical Centers Using Different Questionnaires Through Score Predictors. *Front. Neurosci.*, vol. 16, no. March, pp. 1–12, Mar. 2022, doi: 10.3389/fnins.2022.818686.

Schleicher, M., Pryss, R., Schlee, W., & Spiliopoulou, M. (2022a). When can I expect the mHealth user to return? Prediction meets time series with gaps. In: *Artificial Intelligence in Medicine: 20th International Conference on Artificial Intelligence in Medicine, AIME 2022*,

Halifax, NS, Canada, June 14–17, 2022, Proceedings, S. 310– 320. Springer, 2022. (best paper award) 10.3389/fnins.2022.836834

Schleicher, M., Hamacher, S., Naujoks, M., Günther, K., Schmidt, T., Pryss, R., Schobel, J., Schlee, W., & Spiliopoulou, M. (2022b). Prediction of declining engagement to self-monitoring apps on the example of tinnitus mHealth data. In: *2022 IEEE 35th International Symposium on Computer-Based Medical Systems (CBMS)*, S. 228–233. IEEE, 2022. 10.1109/CBMS55023.2022.00047

Schleicher, M., Pryss, R., Schobel, J., Schlee, W. & Spiliopoulou, M. (2022c). Expect the gap: A recommender approach to estimate the absenteeism of self-monitoring mHealth app users. In: *2022 IEEE 9th International Conference on Data Science and Advanced Analytics (DSAA)*, S. 1–10, Nov 2022. 10.1109/DSAA54385.2022.10032390

Shahania, S., Unnikrishnan, V., Pryss, R., Kraft, R., Schobel, J., Hannemann, R., ... & Spiliopoulou, M. (2021). User-centric vs whole-stream learning for EMA prediction. In *2021 IEEE 34th International Symposium on Computer-Based Medical Systems (CBMS)* (pp. 307-312). IEEE.

Unnikrishnan, V., Shah, Y., Schleicher, M., Fernández-Viadero, C., Strandzheva, M., Velikova, D., ... & Spiliopoulou, M. (2021). Love thy Neighbours: A Framework for Error-Driven Discovery of Useful Neighbourhoods for One-Step Forecasts on EMA data. In *2021 IEEE 34th International Symposium on Computer-Based Medical Systems (CBMS)* (pp. 295-300). IEEE.